

Benchmarking the HERWIG Event Generator in High-Throughput Computing Infrastructure

A Preliminary Approach to Profiling the Environmental Impact of HEP Computations

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Abstract

This study presents a methodology to profile the energy consumption and CO₂e emissions of High Energy Physics (HEP) software using Intel's RAPL interface on a High-Throughput Computing (HTC) cluster. Power measurements from RAPL were compared with the plug-based Prometheus and Green Algorithms calculator. The methodology was applied to benchmark HERWIG 7.3 for Drell-Yan processes [1] at center-of-mass (CoM) energies $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV and $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV and dijet final states at $\sqrt{s} = 14$ TeV. A functional relation of the form $y(n) = a \cdot n^b + c$ was found between the energy consumed and the number of events, n , compatible with linearity within 3σ at 100 TeV and up to 4.7σ at 13 TeV. Additionally, it was found that up to 10^8 simulated events, the power consumption of the CPU running HERWIG remained constant to a good approximation, suggesting that the energy consumption of the CPU, and therefore the emissions, up to a multiplication factor, can be fully parametrised by the duration of the event generation, a finding supported by previous works [2, 3]. Considering the total events recorded by the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) during 2024 [4], the emissions for generating 10^{16} events were estimated at $(6.75 \pm 1.72) \cdot 10^4$ tonnes of CO₂e for $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV and $(2.86 \pm 2.17) \cdot 10^6$ tonnes of CO₂e for $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV. The large uncertainties, particularly for $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV, arise because the extrapolation extends far beyond the collected data range. Furthermore, allowing the exponent b to vary as a free parameter in the model makes the fit especially sensitive to uncertainties, as small changes in b are exponentially amplified at high values of n . Nevertheless, these results are of great value since they provide an order-of-magnitude estimate of the environmental impact of Monte Carlo event generators at LHC scales.

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I had the opportunity to present my work and results on many occasions, including at WLCG workshops [5, 6], and I would like to thank my supervisors not only for encouraging me to do so but also for identifying and creating the right opportunities for me.

During this project, the foundations were also laid for a GitHub organisation affiliated with The University of Manchester, called UofM-Green-Compute. In doing so, we join the growing efforts of the scientific community to make science not only more rigorous but also more responsible.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background

Computational techniques have always been an important factor in High Energy Physics (HEP) research [7, 8]. These techniques range from machine learning and deep learning, Bayesian and frequentist statistical methods, to Monte Carlo (MC) simulations [7]. These kinds of simulations are the primary focus of this research. In light of upcoming short-term collider projects at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), such as the High-Luminosity LHC (HL-LHC) upgrade, the computational workload is expected to become a major bottleneck due to the vast volume of data that will be collected [8, 9]. This problem gets even more serious when considering long-term projects like the Future Circular Collider (FCC) [10]. The growing need to process increasing volumes of data, combined with the ever-present threat of climate change, has made the assessment of energy efficiency and sustainability in HEP software more relevant than ever before.

To do so, an effective approach is to focus on machines specialised in running highly complex computations and analyses, high-performance computing facilities, and data centres [11]. These machines alone emit almost 100 megatonnes of CO₂e annually [12], which is more than the total emissions from electricity and heat in the United Kingdom in 2021 [13]. This fact, combined with the consideration that the carbon footprint of scientists worldwide ranges from 4 to 25 tonnes of CO₂e per capita per year [14–16], makes this a relevant starting point to evaluate the environmental impact of scientific endeavours.

The European Organisation for Nuclear Research (CERN) is by no means unfamiliar with this challenge. In fact, with the creation of the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) [11], as will be discussed in Section 2.1, it has become a major force in global-scale computing. Given this context, it is natural that the attention of physicists and computer scientists has been particularly focused on the efficiency and sustainability of the software and hardware used in physics research. This is illustrated, for example, by the growing number of studies and investigations in the field of computational efficiency [17], as well as by efforts to develop algorithms optimised for parallel computation on GPUs [9, 18]. This investigation itself joins the broader efforts aimed at addressing the sustainability challenges of HEP software, based on a key premise: MC event generators are extensively used in particle physics and rely heavily on CPU architectures to run, and experiments such as ATLAS devote approximately 70% of their CPU time and 60% of their disk storage solely to Monte Carlo simulations [19]. Consequently, the energy consumption of algorithms employing these techniques must be carefully analysed, evaluated, and optimised.

1.2 Scope and Extension

This work expanded on the research done in the first semester, Sep - Dec 2024, by Ilan Sasson and Luis Miguel Villar Padrino [2], which focused on investigating the carbon footprint of the HERWIG 7.3 Monte Carlo event-generator [20] in an Alienware M15 R6 laptop. In this work, however, the simulations were conducted on a High Throughput Computing Cluster, specifically the Noether Cluster at the University of Manchester, which will be introduced in Section 3.1, instead of on a personal laptop. Compared to last semester, this change in hardware environment represents a natural progression of the project, as computing clusters rather than personal computers (PCs) are typically employed for large-scale MC simulations. Additionally, a process beyond Drell-Yan [1] was considered—namely, dijet final states—. In addition to these new implementations, additional profiling tools will be used to compare with the previously utilised CodeCarbon, described in Section 3.2.3. The following sections will present the technical details of HERWIG, Monte Carlo event generators, and the computing infrastructure (HPC and HTC); Section 3, introduced later, will detail the additional software tools used in this study.

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 Worldwide LHC Computing Grid

The European Organisation for Nuclear Research (CERN) is a vast research organisation comprising 24 member states, 10 associate member states, two observer states, and many more with cooperation agreements [21]. This high number of involved parties resulted in an essentially global collaboration, which brought about significant logistical challenges that needed to be addressed in addition to the intrinsic limitations of conducting computationally demanding research, such as data volume and resources. To address these issues, the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG) project was established

in 2001 and finally launched in 2008 [22]. The WLCG is responsible for distributing the data collected by the LHC and providing data storage and analysis resources to physicists across more than 170 sites in 42 countries [11]. By 2017, the grid processed over 100 petabytes of data each year and counted around 500,000 CPU cores distributed globally [23], from which about 20% were provided by CERN. This number has likely increased significantly, considering that by 2024, ATLAS was utilising approximately 700,000 cores [24], according to Zach Marshall, ATLAS Computing Co-Coordinator.

The WLCG is a hierarchical system comprising three computing centres: Tier-0, Tier-1, and Tier-2. Tier-0 refers to the CERN Data Centre, which accounts for approximately 20% of the total computing capacity of the grid [25]. It is responsible for storing the raw data from the LHC experiments and performing the initial data processing, which transforms the raw signals into meaningful physical objects before distributing the data to Tier-1 facilities. Fourteen Tier-1 computer centres worldwide are responsible for storing and reprocessing data received by the Tier-0 layer. They also distribute relevant datasets to the Tier-2 layer, comprising centres typically associated with universities and research institutes. These facilities are primarily used for physics analysis, serving as the main sites where meaningful results are extracted from experimental data. In addition, they play a key role in MC simulations and data reconstruction tasks.

The WLCG also recognises an unofficial Tier-3 layer comprising smaller, locally managed computing resources. These Tier-3 centres operate independently and have no formal obligations to the grid, typically serving individual researchers or research groups for analysis and development tasks. For this research, a Tier-3 computing cluster called the Noether Cluster was utilised, as will be described in Section 3.1.

2.2 HERWIG and Monte Carlo Event-Generators

This section outlines the main features of HERWIG and Monte Carlo event-generators [7], with a focus on specific aspects relevant to the continuation of the thesis presented in [2]. For a more detailed explanation of Monte Carlo event-generators and a historical overview of HERWIG, one may refer to the work presented in [2].

HERWIG is a software tool used in HEP and functions as a general-purpose event generator. Its primary role is to simulate all aspects of particle collisions, except for particle interactions with the detector (this part is typically handled by dedicated software such as GEANT4 [26]). The stages involved in the event generation process were already mentioned in the previous stage of this investigation [2] and are outlined as follows [27, 28]:

- **Hard Process:** The initial high-energy interaction between partons, typically resulting in the production of heavy particles such as top quarks (t), electroweak bosons (W^\pm and Z^0), or Higgs bosons (H).
- **Parton Shower:** The evolution of outgoing partons via successive gluons (g) and quark(q)-antiquark(\bar{q}) pairs emissions. In this step, the structure of jets, discussed in Section 2.3.2, is simulated.
- **Underlying Event:** The collection of additional, less energetic interactions accompanying the hard scatter. These contribute significantly to the overall final-state activity in hadron collisions.
- **Hadronisation :** The process in which coloured partons transform into colour-singlet hadrons due to confinement [29]. It is modelled using phenomenological approaches such as the cluster model (used in HERWIG) [30] or string fragmentation [31].

These stages are essential for a comprehensive understanding of the physics described by the Standard Model; moreover, the predictions produced by Monte Carlo event generators are regarded as crucial for testing theoretical models against experimental data [7].

To be able to do all this, HERWIG 7.3 interfaces with MG5_aMC@NLO [32], a software package used to generate matrix elements at both leading order (LO) and next-to-leading order (NLO). The term LO denotes calculations that rely only on the simplest Feynman diagrams and provide a rough estimate of the cross section of a given process. In contrast, NLO calculations include additional corrections, resulting in greater precision. MG5_aMC@NLO can also simulate parton showers and combine them with the matrix element calculation, ensuring a more accurate and realistic event description. It is worth noting that ‘MG5’ refers to MadGraph5 [33], which is responsible for calculating matrix elements at LO. The ‘aMC@NLO’ part stands for ‘automated MadGraph with NLO capabilities’, which allows the software to perform NLO computations and handle the matching¹ to parton showers. MG5_aMC@NLO often relies on OpenLoops [34], a tool designed for the fast

¹Matching combines NLO matrix elements with parton showers for a single process without double counting emissions. On the other hand, Merging combines matrix elements for multiple jets to improve the description of events with varying numbers of jets.

and automated computation of one-loop scattering amplitudes, to compute the corrections required for NLO calculations efficiently.

It is important to note that HERWIG is not the only general-purpose event generator; other tools, such as PYTHIA and SHERPA [35], are widely used by particle physicists around the globe. Nevertheless, HERWIG is a robust event-generator that performs exceptionally well in QCD-related calculations. This, combined with the advantage of having one of its developers, Prof. Michael Seymour, based in the department at the University, made HERWIG a natural choice for benchmarking in this study.

2.2.1 HERWIG Workflow

The HERWIG workflow consists, in broad terms, of creating an `.in` file (e.g. `LHC-Matchbox.in`), which contains all the necessary instructions for the subsequent event generation. These instructions include the process to be simulated, the CoM energy \sqrt{s} , the choice between LO or NLO calculations, whether to include an analysis using Rivet [36] (a tool commonly used in HEP for event analysis), and other relevant configuration options. The choice between LO and NLO, as well as the value of \sqrt{s} , significantly affects the execution time.

After the creation of the `.in` file, it is read by HERWIG, using the command

```
Herwig read my_file.in,
```

triggering the first phase of the event generation process, which consists of integrating the matrix element to compute cross-sections and generate phase-space information. At the end of this step, a `.run` file is created. Note that the integration step is not usually parallelised and HERWIG does not include an option to do this in a single command. Nevertheless, Section 4.3 references a method to do so. In this research, however, the integration step used only a single thread, unless otherwise stated. Finally, the newly created `.run` file is executed to generate the desired number of events using the command

```
Herwig run my_file.run -N number -j cores,
```

where ‘number’ is the number of events the user wishes to generate, and ‘cores’ is the number of CPU threads the user wants HERWIG to utilise during generation. Further discussion on CPU usage and threading is provided in Section 3.

Having established an understanding of HERWIG’s workflow, it is now appropriate to discuss the particle physics processes chosen for simulation.

2.3 Selected Particle Physics Processes

2.3.1 Drell-Yan process

The Drell-Yan process is a well-established mechanism in particle physics, involving the annihilation of q and \bar{q} in proton–proton collisions [1]. The Drell-Yan process is purely electroweak at LO; however, it has historically been improved through NLO corrections from Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD), which is the theoretical framework that describes the strong interaction among colour-charged particles, such as quarks and gluons. These QCD corrections enhance the precision of theoretical predictions. As a result, the Drell-Yan process has become a valuable tool for probing the internal structure of the proton [37], particularly through its sensitivity to parton distribution functions (PDFs), which describe how the momentum of a proton is distributed among its constituent quarks and gluons during high-energy collisions. A diagram of this process is presented in Figure 1. The quarks’ annihilation produces a resonance consisting of a highly energetic photon (γ) or Z^0 boson, which later creates a lepton-antilepton pair.

Fig. 1. Diagram of the Drell-Yan Process. The two protons of momenta P_1 and P_2 , interact via a q of momentum $p_1 = P_1 x_1$ and an \bar{q} of momentum $p_2 = P_2 x_2$, where $x_{1/2}$ are the momentum fractions of the partons. Note that the resonance introduced by Drell and Yan was originally a (virtual) γ , but the definition of the process was relaxed to include other massive bosons like Z^0 . Diagram by Luis Miguel Villar Padruno.

It is now possible to investigate this process in a little more detail by focusing on the concept of coupling constant (α_i). In Quantum Field Theory (QFT), the theoretical framework of particle physics [38, 39], the coupling constant quantifies how strongly particles interact through a given force. For example, the Drell-Yan process, in the context of QFT and HERWIG, is of order two in α_{EW} at LO, which corresponds to a term of the form α_{EW}^2 . In the NLO HERWIG runs, the order in α_S (which is zero at LO) increases automatically, incorporating contributions from QCD corrections. These corrections can be of two types: ‘real’ or ‘virtual’, depending on their order in α_S [27]. If the correction is of order one, it is referred to as a real correction; if it is of order two, it is considered a virtual correction. Examples of these corrections are shown in Figure 2. Note that real corrections involve the emission of particles that, in principle, can be detected. In contrast, virtual corrections involve particles that exist only as internal lines in Feynman diagrams and cannot be directly observed.

Fig. 2. Feynman diagrams illustrating representative examples of real and virtual QCD corrections to the Drell–Yan process. Diagram (a) depicts a real correction, in which the final state is modified by the emission of a gluon, leading to a jet that is, in principle, experimentally detectable. In contrast, Diagram (b) shows a virtual correction, where no additional particles appear in the final state, as the correction originates from internal quantum fluctuations. Both corrections involve the strong interaction, characterised by the coupling constant α_S . Diagrams by Luis Miguel Villar Padruno.

2.3.2 Dijet final states ($pp \rightarrow jj$)

Dijet final states refer to a group of processes characterised by the production of two collimated sprays of particles, or jets, resulting from the hadronisation of outgoing quarks or gluons. This study focuses on a specific subset: processes mediated by a gluon propagator. The representative Feynman diagram, shown in Figure 3, involves the annihilation of a quark–antiquark pair and the creation of two quarks or gluons via gluon exchange, which subsequently hadronise into jets.

Fig. 3. Feynman diagrams illustrating the two main final states corresponding to the studied $pp \rightarrow jj$ process at LO. The initial q and \bar{q} have momenta determined by the parton distribution functions (PDFs) inside the proton, similar to the Drell–Yan process. Diagrams by Luis Miguel Villar Padruno.

The Standard Model dijet processes are of particular interest, as they constitute the dominant background in searches for particles beyond the Standard Model (BSM) that decay into dijets [40, 41], including potential dark matter (DM)

candidates, as seen in Figure 4, which are hypothetical particles proposed to account for the unseen mass in the universe. In addition to their relevance in BSM searches, dijet events, much like those from Drell–Yan production, play a crucial role in testing QCD and enabling precision measurements of PDFs and α_S [29]. This is especially relevant in the context of perturbative QCD, which describes the interactions of quarks and gluons at high energies using a series expansion in α_S [29], and helps in understanding the energy range of its validity.

Fig. 4. Feynman diagram of a dijet final state produced via a Z' dark matter mediator. This diagram is of order zero in α_S . Therefore, the background of processes like this is investigated when studying dijet final states mediated by gluon propagators. Diagram by Luis Miguel Villar Padruno.

In dijet processes with a gluon propagator, the strong coupling constant α_S is squared at leading order, while the electroweak coupling constant α_{EW} does not contribute. HERWIG will then increase the power of α_S to account for the previously discussed virtual and real QCD corrections, as shown in Figure 5. Unlike the Drell–Yan case, the electroweak coupling constant remains zero at all orders, making this a purely strong interaction even at NLO.

Fig. 5. Feynman diagrams illustrating representative examples of real and virtual QCD corrections to a dijet final state process involving a gluon propagator. Diagram (a) shows an additional gluon emission, which would be detected as a jet, effectively resulting in a $pp \rightarrow jjj$ final state. In Diagram (b), a virtual vertex correction is shown; this is a vertex correction, which plays an important role in QCD by contributing to the cancellation of infinities in perturbative calculations [42]. Diagrams by Luis Miguel Villar Padruno.

3 Tools and Methodology

3.1 The Noether Cluster

The Noether Cluster is a Tier-3 research computation cluster located in the Physics Department at the University of Manchester. This cluster runs a Linux environment, and the system consists of a login node, used to access the cluster and submit jobs (the concept of jobs will be discussed in detail in Section 3.2.1); job-scheduling nodes, which manage and distribute jobs across the cluster; and working nodes, where the actual computations are performed. These nodes are managed and coordinated through the HTCondor scheduler [43, 44], which will be discussed in Section 3.2.1. It is illustrative to think of the nodes as small computers: they consist of Central Processing Units (CPUs), Random Access Memory (RAM), storage, integrated cooling systems (fans), and sometimes Graphics Processing Units (GPUs). These components draw energy from a Power Supply Unit (PSU), with each node equipped with its own dedicated PSU. Each PSU, in turn, is powered by the Power Distribution Unit (PDU), which is responsible for delivering energy to all the nodes.

3.1.1 Noether’s Central Processing Units

The CPUs are the beating heart of most machines [45]. They consist of several cores, which are physical processing units capable of executing tasks independently. Each core can support multiple threads, which are virtual units of execution that allow the CPU to manage several tasks more efficiently by performing parts of them simultaneously. Although the

parallelisation capability of CPUs is lower than that of GPUs [46], it is still effectively utilised by most modern software, including HERWIG, the subject of this investigation.

The Noether Cluster has two types of CPUs, spread across the working nodes:

1. Intel® Xeon® Gold 5220R CPUs @ 2.20 GHz (96 Threads)
2. Intel® Xeon® CPU E5-2620 v4 @ 2.10 GHz (16 Threads)

The first is the most important for this study, as it is the architecture chosen to run the simulations. The Noether Cluster includes eight of these 96-thread CPUs and twenty 16-thread CPUs. In addition, the cluster provides 9 GPUs.

It is essential to note that the Intel® Xeon® Gold 5220R processor comes with 24 physical cores and supports two threads per core by default, resulting in a total of 48 threads. Nevertheless, it supports 2-socket (2S) scalability, meaning it can be deployed in dual-socket systems where two identical processors work together within the same node. Note that in this context, a socket refers to a physical CPU slot on the motherboard, each capable of housing one processor, so this configuration effectively doubles the available computing resources, enabling up to 48 cores and 96 threads in a single system. This is why the Noether Cluster reports 96 threads.

The Intel® Xeon® Gold 5220R processor has a specified Thermal Design Power (TDP) of 150 W; in a dual-socket (2S) configuration, this results in a combined TDP of 300 W. This number represents the maximum amount of heat the processor is expected to emit under sustained workloads. This value is important as it provides an estimate of the processor's energy requirements and aids in the design of appropriate cooling solutions. However, it is essential to note that TDP \neq Power Draw in most cases; the processor's real-time power consumption can vary depending on workload characteristics and system settings. This is the reason why RAPL, discussed in Section 3.2.2, was used to measure the power consumption of the CPU in almost real-time.

3.2 Software Tools

3.2.1 HTCondor and Jobs

HTCondor is a software developed by the Centre for High Throughput Computing at the University of Wisconsin-Madison [47]. Its primary utility is job scheduling in clusters, and it is designed explicitly for High-Throughput Computing (HTC) environments, a computing paradigm optimised to maximise the total amount of work completed over time, rather than the speed of individual tasks. This makes the Noether Cluster technically an HTC facility rather than an HPC, since HPC systems specialise in maximising the speed of single and complex jobs.

In the context of HTCondor, a job refers to an instruction to execute a specific command, along with its associated resource requirements, input and output files, and execution environment. Each job typically consists of two files: an executable script, such as `my_job.sh`, and a submit file, such as `my_job.sub`. The former contains the instructions to be executed on a compute node, while the latter specifies the resource requirements and defines any input or output file handling. These so-called jobs can generally run across multiple cores, requesting this via the `.sub` file, however, a single job is confined to one machine [47].

3.2.2 Running Average Power Limit (RAPL) on Clusters

RAPL is an Intel-developed interface that monitors energy consumption directly at the hardware level. The readings are exposed through the Linux file system at the following path:

```
/sys/class/powercap/intel-rapl.
```

The directory provides energy readings at the socket (package) level via sub-directories such as `intel-rapl:0` and `intel-rapl:1`. However, by default, RAPL does not expose energy consumption per core. This means that only the power usage per CPU package can be measured. This presents a limitation in shared computing environments, where multiple users may run jobs on different subsets of cores within the same socket. In such cases, it is impossible to isolate the energy usage of a specific user or process, leading to inaccurate measurements of individual workloads. Nevertheless, this limitation can be mitigated by requesting exclusive access to all available cores on a single node. Concerning the uncertainties in the measurements of RAPL, a percentage error of 5% was adopted, as supported by findings in literature [48].

3.2.3 CodeCarbon and The Green Algorithms

CodeCarbon is a Python library that interfaces with the previously discussed RAPL. It allows profiling of custom code sections, a feature that makes it helpful in benchmarking specific instructions, such as HERWIG commands. CodeCarbon tracks the energy consumption of software and then calculates the CO₂e emissions associated using the relation

$$\text{CO}_2\text{e} = E \cdot CI, \quad (3.2.1)$$

where E is the total energy consumed by the software, and CI is the carbon intensity [49], measured in mass of CO₂e over energy consumed. The carbon intensity is an important coefficient that depends on how clean the energy source is, which makes estimating it difficult, mainly because this makes it dependent on the region from which the energy originates. CodeCarbon and this research use data from Our World in Data [50] to identify a country-specific CI .

The Green Algorithms [51] is a project led by Dr Loïc Lannelongue and Prof Michael Inouye, both from the University of Cambridge. This project offers a solution for estimating the carbon footprint of running software across various hardware architectures. As of May 2025, they provided an online calculator and a tool called Green Algorithms 4 HPC (GA4HPC) [52], designed to estimate the energy consumption of computational jobs on HPC clusters running SLURM [53], a cluster management and job scheduling system. Given the limited time available for this project, it was decided to rely solely on the online calculator provided by Green Algorithms, as using GA4HPC would have required modifying the software to ensure compatibility with HTCondor. The methodology used by The Green Algorithms is equivalent to the one used by CodeCarbon, and therefore also uses Equation (3.2.1) to calculate CO₂e. However, they include the RAM power consumption in their energy calculations using the approximation that it contributes a power of 0.3725 W per GB [54, 55].

It is important to note that both CodeCarbon and The Green Algorithms use a coefficient called Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE), the ratio of total energy drawn to energy used by computing equipment, to calculate the CO₂e as

$$\text{CO}_2\text{e} = E_{\text{raw}} \cdot \text{PUE} \cdot CI, \quad (3.2.2)$$

where we now redefine the total energy consumption as $E = E_{\text{raw}} \cdot \text{PUE}$, with E_{raw} representing the raw energy usage, calculated as the power draw reported by the machine. In this study, the PUE was set to unity, as it is merely a scaling factor that can be applied at the end of the calculation. Finally, Equation (3.2.2) can then be rewritten as

$$\text{CO}_2\text{e} = (P_{\text{raw}} \cdot t) \cdot CI, \quad (3.2.3)$$

where P_{raw} is the power consumption of the machine and t is the duration of the computations. From Equation (3.2.3), it can be concluded that, if P_{raw} remains constant, the resulting CO₂e emissions can be fully parametrised by the duration of the workload.

3.2.4 Prometheus

During the project, the decision was made to use a software tool specialised in monitoring system and server metrics, Prometheus [56], to provide a point of comparison for the measurements obtained using RAPL via CodeCarbon. Matt T. Proud and Julius Volz initially developed Prometheus, and most of its early development was supported by the audio streaming service SoundCloud. Today, the software is open-source and not affiliated with any specific company. It relies on a time-series database where all data, such as power consumption, is stored using labels and timestamps (date and time).

Prometheus interfaced with power plugs, which monitored the energy drawn by the PSU of the nodes running targeted HTCondor jobs. As discussed in Section 3.1, these nodes consist of several components beyond the CPU, so the energy measured in this case corresponds to the total energy usage by the node. This fact is important when comparing results with CodeCarbon, since the latter can only measure the CPU's energy consumption.

3.3 HERWIG Execution on Noether Cluster

3.3.1 General Considerations and Workflow

The version of HERWIG employed in this study was HERWIG 7.3, provided by PhD student Siddharth Sule via a custom environment. This environment was used exclusively for this research and remained unmodified throughout the set of runs to ensure the consistency and reproducibility of the results. Additionally, all HTCondor jobs were submitted requesting exactly 96 threads to ensure that the machine in use, the Intel[®] Xeon[®] Gold 5220R CPU, was not shared with other users of the Noether Cluster.

The project workflow can be better understood by considering the key files used for profiling: the `master.sh` script, the `Run.py` script, and the job-related files (e.g., `.sub` and `.sh` files). In the remainder of this subsection, we will focus on explaining the content and functionality of these files, as well as highlighting the relationships between them:

- `Run.py`: This is a python file that initializes the CodeCarbon tracking system and runs HERWIG commands in the shell using a user-defined function. It also ensures that the integration and generation phases of the event generation are profiled independently, thereby obtaining CO₂e emission estimates for each phase.
- `job.sh`: The executable copies all important files (e.g., the `.in` file and the `Run.py` file) to the temporary working node provided by HTCondor, and then executes `Run.py`. Finally, it moves the emission files created by the python script to the user's directory.
- `job.sub`: The submission file requests a specific number of threads, memory, and disk space from the scheduler. For this research, the values were 16 GB for both disk and memory, and 96 threads.
- `master.sh`: This is a shell script executed as a background process, using the `nohup` command. It is responsible for:
 1. Submitting Condor jobs using the appropriate `.sub` and `.sh` files.
 2. Waiting for the Condor jobs to finish execution to avoid overlap between jobs with different parameters (such as different CoM energies, \sqrt{s} , or final states).
 3. Merging all emission `.csv` files using an auxiliary 'merging' job.
 4. Modifying all necessary files for the next set of runs, including the `.in` file and the `Run.py` file, depending on the process under consideration.

In summary, the `master.sh` script is run using `nohup`; it manages the submission of jobs and data transfer, ultimately producing `.csv` files containing the CodeCarbon measurements.

Finally, after all jobs are completed, the power consumption data collected via Prometheus is compared with the CodeCarbon readings. Again, it is important to note that Prometheus monitors the entire working node and reflects the power draw of the entire machine, not only the CPU. At this stage, the Green Algorithms calculator is also consulted.

As discussed, two particle physics processes were selected for simulation: the Drell–Yan process and dijet final states of the form $pp \rightarrow jj$ mediated by gluon propagators. The methodology is similar in both cases, and only specific considerations relevant to each process will be discussed in the following subsections.

3.3.2 Drell-Yan

As previously discussed, the Drell–Yan process was the first benchmarked process. Following prior studies [2], the CoM energies used in the `.in` file, named `LHC-Matchbox.in`, were $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV and $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV. These values were chosen to reflect the typical operating energy of the LHC between 2015 and 2018, as well as the projected capabilities of the FCC. A list of additional simulation characteristics is provided in Table 1. Among the most relevant are the use of MadGraph and OpenLoops to compute NLO corrections, as well as the applied invariant mass cuts for the final-state leptons, which are set between 60 GeV and 130 GeV, to target Z^0 resonances.

Category	Setting
Centre-of-mass energy	$\sqrt{s} = 13 \text{ TeV}$ or $\sqrt{s} = 100 \text{ TeV}$
Physics process	$pp \rightarrow e^+e^-, \mu^+\mu^-$ or $\tau^+\tau^-$
Coupling constant order	α_{EW}^2
Matrix element provider	MadGraph-OpenLoops
NLO correction order	Included via OpenLoops
Lepton pair mass cut	$60 < m_{\ell+\ell^-} < 130 \text{ GeV}$
Parton shower matching	MCatNLO with default shower

Table 1. Simulation settings for the Drell–Yan process. The table summarises the main parameters used in the `LHC-Matchbox.in` file, including the electroweak coupling constant order, matrix element providers, and NLO corrections.

The workflow described in the previous Section 3.3.1 outlines the general methodology used for the Drell–Yan simulations, but there are a few additional caveats. The `master.sh` script implemented a triple loop: firstly over the two CoM energies, $\sqrt{s} = 13 \text{ TeV}$ and $\sqrt{s} = 100 \text{ TeV}$; secondly, over the three considered processes, $pp \rightarrow e^+e^-$, $pp \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$, and $pp \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$; and lastly, over the set $N = 0, 1, 2, \dots$. Here, N is defined such that

$$n = 10^N, \quad (3.3.1)$$

where n represents the number of events generated, this is why N is referred to as the ‘order’ of the simulation. Eight jobs were submitted to HTCondor during each iteration, ensuring all files had the correct settings. These jobs produced two `.csv` files named: `Gen(Int)_emissionsN=order_P=process_E=energy.csv`, where ‘order’, ‘process’ and ‘energy’ are just numbers labeling the iterations. These files correspond to the CodeCarbon output for the generation (Gen) and integration (Int) phases of the event generation.

It should be noted that, for this study, the number of events simulated was $n = 10^8$ for $\sqrt{s} = 13 \text{ TeV}$ and $n = 10^6$ for $\sqrt{s} = 100 \text{ TeV}$. This choice did affect the uncertainties of the results; however, it was necessary due to time constraints, as the $\sqrt{s} = 100 \text{ TeV}$ simulations were incredibly long.

3.3.3 Dijet Final States

The CoM energy chosen for this set of simulations was $\sqrt{s} = 14 \text{ TeV}$, which corresponds to the design energy of the LHC and is close to its current operating energy of 13.6 TeV. The key difference between the previous methodology and this one is the usage of merging instead of matching for the `.in` file, called: `LHC-J-Merging.in`. The key features of this file are shown in Table 2, but the most important ones are the \sqrt{s} and the NLO treatment.

Category	Setting
Centre-of-mass energy	$\sqrt{s} = 14 \text{ TeV}$
Physics process	$pp \rightarrow jj$
Coupling constant order	α_S^2
Matrix element provider	MadGraph-OpenLoops
NLO correction order	Included via OpenLoops
Parton shower	Dipole parton shower

Table 2. Simulation settings for the dijet process. The table summarises the main parameters used in the `LHC-J-Merging.in` file, including the coupling constant order, matrix element providers and NLO corrections.

The dijet methodology was straightforward compared to the Drell–Yan implementation. It consisted of utilising the HTCondor jobs and `Run.py` to benchmark the integration phase of the dijet event generation. Note that only the integration phase was benchmarked for dijets due to time constraints.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Results of Drell-Yan Simulations

4.1.1 Integration Phase

Analysis of the HTCondor logs confirmed that the integration phase of the HERWIG workflow utilised a single CPU thread, as expected. This means that, out of the 96 available threads, only one was used. The power consumption calculated using CodeCarbon and the duration of the runs are displayed in Table 3. The average power consumption is much lower than the CPU's 300 W TDP.

Process	Power Consumption of CPU (W)	Duration (s)
$pp \rightarrow e^+e^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV	96.01 ± 3.02	737.30 ± 5.87
$pp \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV	95.17 ± 3.03	751.93 ± 8.64
$pp \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV	95.71 ± 2.63	949.21 ± 8.15
$pp \rightarrow e^+e^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV	94.65 ± 3.56	732.15 ± 11.63
$pp \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV	97.15 ± 2.99	701.56 ± 6.07
$pp \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV	97.37 ± 2.74	890.77 ± 7.64
Weighted Mean	96.11 ± 1.21	

Table 3. Durations of the runs and mean power consumption of the CPU, measured via CodeCarbon, with associated uncertainties for different final states. The uncertainties account for the CodeCarbon time resolution, a 5% uncertainty in RAPL measurements, and statistical variation across simulations.

When using Prometheus, which profiles the entire machine via the PSU, the power consumption calculated per process is naturally higher and summarised in Table 4. The durations of the runs were taken to be those reported by CodeCarbon. The mean power consumption reported by Prometheus was 144.51 ± 0.30 W, which is approximately 50 W higher than the value reported by CodeCarbon. This is, as mentioned, natural, considering that Prometheus measures the PSU and not only the CPU. Nevertheless, these numbers suggest that the CPU is the primary contributor to the total power consumption of the working node.

Process	Power Consumption PSU (W)	Duration (s)
$pp \rightarrow e^+e^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV	145.27 ± 0.75	737.30 ± 5.87
$pp \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV	143.60 ± 0.73	751.93 ± 8.64
$pp \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV	145.82 ± 0.82	949.21 ± 8.15
$pp \rightarrow e^+e^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV	141.60 ± 0.74	732.15 ± 11.63
$pp \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV	145.37 ± 0.79	701.56 ± 6.07
$pp \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV	145.41 ± 0.62	890.77 ± 7.64
Weighted Mean	144.51 ± 0.30	

Table 4. Mean power consumption during the integration phase, measured using power plugs interfaced by Prometheus, for different final states and CoM energies.

Notably, the duration of the simulations differs between the processes and energies considered. This observation highlights which processes are the most computationally demanding to calculate. The $pp \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ channel is the most complex of the three at both energies. It is particularly interesting and worth noting that the three durations at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV appear to decrease when moving to $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV.

4.1.2 Generation Phase

In this subsection, the results are presented in two parts: the first focuses on the CPU and PSU's power consumption, as before, and the second explores the functional relation between the CO₂e emissions and the number of events generated.

Power Consumption

During the generation phase, the software utilised all 96 CPU threads, as confirmed by the HTCondor logs. As expected, the power consumption in this phase was higher than during the integration phase. The corresponding CodeCarbon and Prometheus measurements are summarised in Table 5. It is worth noting that CodeCarbon uses a measurement interval of 15 seconds, so short simulations are not statistically meaningful, and this was taken into account by introducing an error in the duration and taking the weighted mean.

Tool	Weighted Mean Power (W)	CPU or PSU
CodeCarbon	286.83 ± 3.07	CPU
Prometheus	362.76 ± 2.35	PSU

Table 5. Weighted mean power consumption measured by CodeCarbon and Prometheus. Note that CodeCarbon reports only the CPU power consumption, whereas Prometheus measures the power consumption of the entire machine via the PSU

For the event generation phase, the energy measured for the CPU using CodeCarbon was 286.83 ± 3.07 W, which is comparable to the reported TDP of the processor used in these studies. On the other hand, the power consumption measured by Prometheus was once again higher, by approximately 76 W. A comparison with the Green Algorithms calculator shows agreement within an order of magnitude. The calculator was configured using the TDP of the CPU employed in this study and compared against a set of simulations. The generation of up to 10^8 events of the $pp \rightarrow e^+e^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV was considered, yielding an energy consumption estimate of 3.77 ± 0.04 kWh based on the duration of the simulations. On the other hand, CodeCarbon measured an energy consumption of 3.66 ± 0.09 kWh. These two values are compatible, as indicated by their z -score, defined as the difference between the means divided by the quadrature sum of their uncertainties, which yields $z \simeq 1.12$.

Energy vs Number of Events

This study found a combination of a constant and a power law relationship between the number of events simulated, n , and the energy consumption (and therefore the emissions up to a factor CI),

$$E = a \cdot n^b + c, \quad (4.1.1)$$

where a , b , and c are constants determined by the fitting algorithm. This relation holds for all final states considered, and for both $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV and $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV. Since the behaviour is consistent across all cases, only the $pp \rightarrow e^+e^-$ process will be presented in the body of this report, as the conclusions also apply to the other processes. All plots, nevertheless, are presented in the Appendix. The relationship between n and E is presented in Figure 6. The fit yielded a reduced chi-squared value of $\chi_{\text{red}}^2 = 0.36$. This value is somewhat low considering the target of $\chi_{\text{red}}^2 \sim 1$; this means that the model could be overfitting the data, however, it captures its trend. The χ_{red}^2 values for the remaining processes can be found in Table 6.

Fig. 6. Cumulative energy draw when running HERWIG 7.3 for $pp \rightarrow e^+e^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV. The relationship follows the form $\text{CO}_2e = a \cdot n^b + c$, where a , b , and c are constants obtained from the fit. Note that for sufficiently large n , the term c becomes negligible, and the plot appears almost linear even on a log-log scale. The calculated reduced chi-squared was $\chi^2_{\text{red}} = 0.36$, which is lower than the ideal target of $\chi^2_{\text{red}} \sim 1$. This suggests that the data may be slightly overfitted, likely due to the inclusion of the exponent b in the model. While a simpler model could yield a higher χ^2_{red} , the power-law plus constant form captures subtle deviations from linearity across different processes more effectively. Plot by Luis Miguel Villar Padrino.

A notable result is that the model deviates from the linear relationship identified in [2]. Examining the values of the exponent b , we find that for both CoM energies, the model remains consistent with linearity within approximately 3σ , except for the particular case of $pp \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$, which shows a deviation of almost 5σ . However, one should note that these deviations are at most 0.1. At the current state of the field, it is reasonable to consider that these models are, to a good approximation, linear. However, further research is needed to explore the relationship between the number of events and the energy consumed in depth. This is especially important given that, for a sufficiently large number of events, even slight deviations from linearity can significantly impact the final estimated energy consumption.

Process	$(a \pm \delta a) \cdot 10^{-9}$	$b \pm \delta b$	$(c \pm \delta c) \cdot 10^{-5}$	χ^2_{red}
$pp \rightarrow e^+e^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV	44.1 ± 8.2	0.988 ± 0.012	205 ± 5	0.36
$pp \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV	21.8 ± 4	1.037 ± 0.012	50 ± 1	1.02
$pp \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV	19.8 ± 3.9	1.056 ± 0.012	216 ± 1	1.27
$pp \rightarrow e^+e^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV	25.8 ± 10.4	1.104 ± 0.032	217 ± 5	0.41
$pp \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV	29.8 ± 1.2	1.097 ± 0.031	215 ± 5	0.40
$pp \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV	29.2 ± 1.1	1.104 ± 0.031	218 ± 6	0.68

Table 6. Fit parameters with uncertainties for the model $y = a \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot n^b + c \cdot 10^{-5}$, and corresponding reduced chi-squared values.

Most of the χ^2_{red} values are under the ideal value of one, and therefore the model is overfitting the data. This could be either an overestimation of the uncertainties, mostly RAPL, or a poor choice of model. The latter was discarded since many models were also fitted, yielding much higher and lower χ^2_{red} .

Using these fits, a prediction was made for the CO_2e emissions associated with running HERWIG, parametrised by the number of generated events. This extrapolation, visible in Figure 7, shows the expected emissions of generating up to $n = 10^{16}$ events, motivated by the fact that the LHC records around 10^{16} events each year [4]. As mentioned earlier, for $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV, events were generated only up to $n = 10^6$, resulting in larger uncertainties compared to the $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV case, for which up to 10^8 events were simulated. In addition, since the uncertainty in RAPL readings was taken as a fixed percentage of the measured value (set to 5%), the associated error increases more rapidly for computationally demanding processes. This is reflected in the broader uncertainty region shown in Figure 7.

On the other hand, the CO₂e emissions predicted for $pp \rightarrow e^+e^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV at $n = 10^{16}$ are around half than those estimated in previous works [2]. This apparent discrepancy stems from two distinct sources. First, during the initial semester of this study, the event generation phase was not parallelised, and as a result, the durations were significantly longer than they should have been. Second, in that earlier study, a constraint was imposed requiring the functional relationship to be linear, thus fixing the exponent to $b = 1$. In the case of $pp \rightarrow e^+e^-$, the fitted value of b was less than one; this fact shrunk the extrapolation results. The floating value of the exponent of the fitted model also explains why, in this study, the predicted emissions for $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV are higher, since for all processes at this CoM, the model was superlinear.

The estimated CO₂e emissions were $(6.75 \pm 1.72) \cdot 10^4$ tonnes for $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV and $(2.86 \pm 2.17) \cdot 10^6$ tonnes for $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV. It should be noted that these large uncertainties arise from extrapolating to a region eight orders of magnitude beyond the range in which the data were collected. Moreover, relaxing the constraint $b = 1$, used in previous studies [2], significantly impacted the model's behaviour at high values of n . For instance, when strictly enforcing $b = 1$, the predicted emissions for $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV decrease by one order of magnitude, and the uncertainty by three. Notwithstanding, a perfectly linear fit of the data yields a $\chi_{\text{red}}^2 \ll 1$ for $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV and $\chi_{\text{red}}^2 \gg 1$ for $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV.

Fig. 7. A comparison is shown of the emissions associated with running HERWIG for the process $pp \rightarrow e^+e^-$ at both $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV and $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV. These extrapolations were made based on the models fitted to the data, including the uncertainties in their parameters. The shadowed areas represent the 1σ confidence regions. As expected, generating Drell-Yan events at higher energies results in greater CO₂e emissions; this occurs because the simulation durations are longer, further confirming that the duration of the simulation is the most influential parameter. Plot by Luis Miguel Villar Padruno.

Reassessment of Last Semester's Results

As mentioned above, the work conducted last semester on an 11th Gen Intel Core i7-11800H @ 2.30 GHz CPU did not parallelise HERWIG's event generation phase. Therefore, in this brief section, an updated set of measurements is presented to ensure completeness and enable a fair comparison with the Noether Cluster.

The average power consumption during the generation phase, utilising all available cores on the laptop's CPU, was measured to be $P_{\text{laptop}}^{\text{gen}} = 54.8 \pm 8.6$ W. In contrast, the power consumption during the integration phase corresponded to the value reported last semester, $P_{\text{laptop}}^{\text{int}} = 24.7 \pm 1.4$ W. Additionally, new models of the form $\text{CO}_2\text{e} = a \cdot n^b + c$ were fitted to the data, and therefore new predictions for the CO₂e emissions were established, shown in Figure 8. The results of the fits will be shown in the Appendix, as only the final results will be used for comparison.

Fig. 8. Predicted CO₂e emissions associated with the generation of n events on an 11th Gen Intel Core i7-11800H @ 2.30 GHz CPU. It should be noted that GPU energy consumption was neglected, as this hardware was not utilised by HERWIG in these simulations. Plot by Luis Miguel Villar Padrano.

Regarding the large uncertainties shown in Figure 8, it is important to note that for the laptop studies, only up to 10^5 events were simulated, and therefore the fit is less significant. Nevertheless, the observed trend is consistent with that identified on the Noether Cluster. A seemingly unexpected result was that the number of events generated per unit of CPU energy consumed was higher for the laptop than for the Noether Cluster, indicating that event generation on the laptop is more energy efficient. This is illustrated in Figure 9, and the fitted function was

$$f(n) = \frac{a \cdot n}{1 + c \cdot n}, \quad (4.1.2)$$

where a and c are redefined constants for this model; this relationship captures a constant efficiency for sufficiently large numbers of simulated events. However, this model is an approximation, since thermal throttling (the CPU slows down to prevent overheating, reducing performance) will eventually occur during sufficiently long simulations.

Fig. 9. Comparison of the number of events generated per unit of energy consumption for the Noether Cluster and the laptop. As shown in the plot, the laptop exhibits higher energy efficiency. The reduced chi-squared values of both fits are acceptable, supporting the conclusion that behaviour is well described by the proposed functional relationship. At sufficiently large n , the expected efficiency of the laptop approaches approximately 30,000 events/Wh, whereas the Noether Cluster reaches a maximum efficiency of around 24,000 events/Wh. Note that, for the laptop case, this claim assumes the model can be extrapolated for higher n , but thermal throttling is expected to occur. Plot by Luis Miguel Villar Padrano.

After reaching this conclusion, an obvious question arises: why not use laptops for event generation? The answer is simple: time. In Figure 10, a plot of n over the durations of generations is shown. For short generations, $n < 10^4$, the laptop outperforms the cluster; nevertheless, beyond this point, the Noether Cluster becomes much faster than the laptop.

Fig. 10. Plot of the number of events generated over time. Beyond $n = 10^4$, the CPU of the Cluster outperforms that of the laptop. The reduced chi-squared values of both fits are satisfactory, with a mild overfitting for the Noether Cluster model. Plot by Luis Miguel Villar Padruno.

A quantity ε can be defined as the number of events generated per unit time per unit energy. The plot of ε versus the number of events generated is shown in Figure 11. The fit that best described the data was

$$g(n) = \frac{a \cdot n^b}{1 + c \cdot n^d} \quad (4.1.3)$$

where all constants, a , b , c and d are constants of the model. It can be seen that, for low values of n , ε is greater for the laptop. However, the cluster becomes more efficient beyond $n = 10^5$ events. It is important to consider that beyond $n = 10^5$ events, no data was taken for the laptop. Therefore, making predictions past this point is unreliable due to thermal throttling.

Fig. 11. Plot of ε . Beyond $n = 10^5$, the CPU of the cluster outperforms that of the laptop, but the behaviour of the laptop after this point is unclear due to the lack of data points and known thermal effects such as thermal throttling. The reduced chi-squared values of both fits are satisfactory, with a mild overfitting observed in the Noether Cluster model. Plot by Luis Miguel Villar Padruno.

A preliminary conclusion that can be drawn from these results is that, surprisingly, the laptop appears to be more energy-efficient than the cluster. However, this becomes less surprising when considering that laptops are specifically designed to operate efficiently on battery power. On the other hand, the energy reported by CodeCarbon reflects only the consumption of the CPU and RAM. In the case of the laptop, however, there are several additional components drawing power, such as the display and GPU, and none of these can be considered negligible. Additionally, one must consider that thermal throttling will occur when the CPU is engaged for long enough, which will decrease its efficiency significantly.

4.2 Results of Dijet Simulations

The integration phase of the dijet final states, similar to the Drell–Yan case, utilises only a single CPU thread, as reported by HTCondor; consequently, a similar power consumption to that observed for the Drell–Yan process is expected for the dijet case. As anticipated, the measured power consumption was found to be 98.77 ± 0.95 W, a value highly compatible with that obtained from the Drell–Yan integration phase, 96.11 ± 1.21 W, their compatibility is evidenced by their z -score $z \simeq 1.73$. It should be noted that these simulations took significantly longer than the Drell–Yan integrations, around 15 hours, reflecting the greater complexity of the merging algorithm compared to the matching. Using Prometheus data, the average power consumption of the integration phase was found to be 146.16 ± 0.10 W, which is lower than the 144.51 ± 0.30 W measured for the Drell–Yan case; this time, the difference is significant ($z \simeq 5.2$). Nevertheless, one must remember that the uncertainties are underestimated for the Prometheus data, since no measurement error was considered, only the simulation durations and the statistical uncertainty from repeated measurements.

It has been stated that the integration phase of this process alone takes approximately 15 hours of computing time. This raises the question: why is thermal throttling not observed in the results, given the extended runtime? Power consumption measurements show an almost perfectly constant value throughout. This happens because, during the integration phase, only one thread is active, so the CPU temperature remains relatively low compared to scenarios where all cores are fully utilised, like the generation phase. Since the temperature stays within the processor’s thermal operating limits, there is no need for the system to reduce its clock speed, and thus, no thermal throttling occurs.

4.3 General Discussion

Event Generation vs Integration

It is important to note that, for simple processes such as Drell–Yan, the event generation phase is significantly more impactful in terms of emissions compared to the integration phase (and this is always the case if the integration phase is parallelised). Therefore, understanding the functional relationship between the number of events and the associated emissions is a valuable tool for assessing the environmental impact of the data produced by event generators. In fact, this study alone resulted in approximately 50 kg of CO₂e emissions.

In relation to the model which describes the emissions/energy as a function of n , given that the exponent, b , changes with the final state considered, it can be inferred that either the physics of the process might affect the functional relationship or the cluster might have experienced thermal effects like throttling when simulating more computationally demanding final states. Regardless, further study is advised in this direction. Nevertheless, it should be noted that, so far, the variation in b lies within the margin of error of 5σ , and the maximum deviation corresponds to 0.1. Thus, the relationship can be approximated as linear for sufficiently low n .

Laptop vs Cluster

Comparing the results of Drell–Yan from this semester and last semester [2], it is possible to see how important the parallelisation of the generation phase is. Even when using more energy, parallelisation does make the process quicker and, in most cases, greener. On the other hand, it was previously stated that the laptop produced more events per unit energy, which is correct. However, the runtime of the simulations is significantly longer on the laptop, making it impractical for physicists to rely on such machines, as was evidenced in Section 4.1.2. Additionally, HPCC and HTCC are designed to operate nearly 24 hours a day, every day of the week, which is difficult to achieve with a personal computer. On the other hand, it was also shown that the number of events per unit time per unit energy, ε , was higher for the cluster for sufficiently large n , but, as previously stated, no conclusions can be drawn for laptops ε beyond $n = 10^5$, so more data must be taken for this regime, nonetheless, thermal effects are expected.

Dijets vs Drell–Yan

Focusing on the dijet and Drell-Yan processes, it is plausible to arrive at the same conclusion as in previous works [2] [3]: the ‘greenness’ of the software can be quantified by its runtime duration to a good approximation. More complex algorithms, such as the one used for dijets, take a significantly longer amount of time to complete. However, the machine’s power consumption, and consequently, the emission rate, remained roughly constant throughout the run, at least when the CPU was not fully engaged. That said, thermal throttling is expected when the entire CPU works at full capacity for a long time. A recommendation for this long process is to parallelise the integration using HERWIG’s default method described on their webpage [30]. Following their recommendations reduces the duration from 15 hours to around 400 seconds, making it approximately 135 times faster. Due to time constraints, it was impossible to assess the generation phase of the dijet final states. However, the results are expected to be similar to those obtained for Drell-Yan, with key differences coming from the run-time and thermal effects alone.

5 Conclusions and Future Work

5.1 Conclusions

This study contributes to the growing field of sustainable scientific computing by applying a methodology to quantify the energy consumption and CO₂e emissions associated with MC simulations in HEP. This was achieved using the HERWIG event generator, executed on an Intel® Xeon® Gold 5220R CPU @ 2.20 GHz from the Noether Cluster. Two physical processes were analysed: the Drell-Yan process at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV and $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV, as well as dijet production involving a gluon propagator at $\sqrt{s} = 14$ TeV.

The results of this study confirmed that the CPU power draw remained stable during the integration phase of the HERWIG workflow to a very good approximation, whilst minor deviations were noticed for the generation phase, likely due to thermal effects. Consequently, emissions can be effectively parametrised by the time the program is run on a given hardware platform. Additional profiling tools, such as The Green Algorithms and Prometheus, were employed to validate the results obtained through CodeCarbon. Both tools supported the fundamental assumptions underlying this approach. In addition, a power-law plus constant model was found to best describe the relationship between energy consumption and number of events generated; moreover, a deviation from linearity was observed to almost 5σ for $pp \rightarrow \tau^+ \tau^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV. These findings suggest that estimating the energy consumed might be less straightforward than just considering the relation outlined in Equation (3.2.3) and assuming a constant power consumption. More investigation is encouraged in this direction, especially to assess how thermal effects might affect the results and current paradigms on how we estimate CO₂e emissions.

As mentioned in the discussion above, around 50 kg of CO₂e were already emitted in this study alone. This highlights how easily the environmental impact of our work as physicists can be underestimated and how frequently such emissions occur without researchers being fully aware of them. The extrapolation for the $pp \rightarrow e^+ e^-$ process estimated that 67 kt of CO₂e would be emitted for $n = 10^{16}$ simulated events at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV. This figure only increases for $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV, for which the predicted emissions are on the order of millions of tonnes of CO₂e. These estimates account solely for CPU energy consumption; however, additional emissions must be expected due to cooling systems, memory usage, data transfer, and other infrastructure components. The challenge now is recognising the role of physicists and researchers in addressing climate change and proposing solutions and strategies that allow continued scientific progress without stagnation.

5.2 Future Work

5.2.1 Developments of this Work

A valuable addition to this research would be to establish a relationship between power draw and the number of cores engaged and assess how parallelisation saves energy. Additionally, comparing HERWIG’s behaviour across different CPU architectures will provide insights into how these variations impact the software’s runtime and efficiency. In addition, collaboration with other profiling software providers is expected. These could include HEPscore [57] and Scaphandre [58], which will benefit the project by offering additional points of comparison between datasets and methodologies.

The next step in this investigation will be collecting additional data for laptop runs for $n > 10^5$ events to study thermal throttling effects more directly and to allow meaningful comparison with the cluster. Furthermore, benchmarking the generation phase of dijet events remains a priority, and the methodologies presented in this work serve as a solid foundation for pursuing that goal. Additionally, this project has focused solely on HERWIG, so a natural extension of this work would

be to assess the efficiency of other Monte Carlo event generators such as PYTHIA and SHERPA, also available on the Noether Cluster. This comparison would provide a valuable reference point for evaluating efficiency between different generators.

Finally, this investigation would benefit from a dedicated team taking charge of a study to complete the hardware’s life cycle assessment (LCA). Thus far, only their operational energy use has been considered. At the same time, the production and disposal stages, both key phases in the life cycle of any electronic device, have not yet been addressed. However, work in this direction is underway by Nicolas Labra et al. in the Department of Engineering of the University of Manchester.

5.2.2 Developments of the Field

The study of software sustainability and efficiency in HEP is a relatively new but rapidly growing area of research. As computing continues to play a central role in particle physics, there is increasing awareness of the need to balance performance with environmental responsibility. This opens up a wide range of opportunities for interdisciplinary contributions from both physicists and computer scientists.

One of the most promising directions involves the development of event generators and computational tools that can use GPU’s parallelisation capabilities. Recent studies have demonstrated the feasibility of modifying algorithms to exploit GPU architectures effectively [9, 18, 59, 60]. At the same time, there are significant efforts in optimising existing algorithms [61, 62].

Integrating sustainability metrics into job scheduling systems like HTCondor is a valuable practice for the future –some systems already incorporate such features, for example, PanDA [63], used in ATLAS– since comprehensive, real-time metrics for power consumption and CO₂e emissions would allow the scientific community to make more informed decisions regarding the use of computing resources.

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Appendices

A Plots

A.1 Drell-Yan Energy vs Events at 13TeV

Fig. A.1. Cumulative energy draw when running HERWIG 7.3 for $pp \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV. The calculated reduced chi-squared was $\chi_{\text{red}}^2 = 1.02$, suggesting that both the fit and the errors considered are highly compatible. In this case, the exponent of the model, b , equals 1.04, that is 3σ away from unity. Plot by Luis Miguel Villar Padruno.

Fig. A.2. Cumulative energy draw when running HERWIG 7.3 for $pp \rightarrow \tau^+ \tau^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV. The calculated reduced chi-squared was $\chi^2_{\text{red}} = 1.27$, this number once more suggests a good fit. An interesting note, nonetheless, is the fact that the exponent b of the model deviates from unity, but remains within 5σ , the significance is of 4.67σ . This is a high deviation that suggests that the physics of the process might modify the relationship between energy and n . Plot by Luis Miguel Villar Padruno.

A.2 Drell-Yan Energy vs Events at 100TeV

Fig. A.3. Cumulative energy draw when running HERWIG 7.3 for $pp \rightarrow e^+e^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV. The calculated reduced chi-squared was $\chi_{\text{red}}^2 = 0.41$, suggesting that some overfitting was performed. Again, a deviation from linearity was found, the exponent, b , was found to be $b = 1.104 \pm 0.032$ which deviates from unity at around 3σ significance. Plot by Luis Miguel Villar Padruno.

Fig. A.4. Cumulative energy draw when running HERWIG7.3 for $pp \rightarrow \tau^+ \tau^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV. The calculated reduced chi-squared was $\chi_{\text{red}}^2 = 0.40$, suggesting that some overfitting was performed. Again, a deviation from linearity was found, the exponent, b , was found to be $b = 1.097 \pm 0.031$ which deviates from unity at around 3σ significance, like the $pp \rightarrow e^+ e^-$ case. Plot by Luis Miguel Villar Padruno.

Fig. A.5. Cumulative energy draw when running HERWIG 7.3 for $pp \rightarrow \tau^+ \tau^-$ at $\sqrt{s} = 100$ TeV. The calculated reduced chi-squared was $\chi_{\text{red}}^2 = 0.40$, suggesting that some overfitting may have occurred. Again, a deviation from linearity was found: the exponent b was calculated to be $b = 1.104 \pm 0.031$, which deviates from unity at around 3σ significance, confirming the trend observed in the other two dilepton final states considered. Plot by Luis Miguel Villar Padruno.

A.3 Efficiency Comparisons: Laptop vs Noether Cluster

A.3.1 $pp \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$

Fig. A.6. Comparison of the number of events generated per unit of energy consumption for the Noether Cluster and the Laptop for $pp \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$. Note that, for the laptop case, this claim is assuming the model can be extrapolated for higher n , but thermal throttling is expected to occur. Plot by Luis Miguel Villar Padrino.

Fig. A.7. Plot of the number of events generated over time for $pp \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^-$. Beyond $n = 10^4$, the CPU of the Cluster outperforms that of the laptop. The reduced chi-squared values of both fits are satisfactory in both cases, with a mild overfitting for the Noether Cluster model. Plot by Luis Miguel Villar Padrino.

A.3.2 $pp \rightarrow \tau^+ \tau^-$

Fig. A.8. Comparison of the number of events generated per unit of energy consumption for the Noether Cluster and the Laptop for $pp \rightarrow \tau^+ \tau^-$. Note that, for the laptop case, this claim is assuming the model can be extrapolated for higher n , but thermal throttling is expected to occur. Plot by Luis Miguel Villar Padruno.

Fig. A.9. Plot of the number of events generated over time for $pp \rightarrow \tau^+ \tau^-$. Beyond $n = 10^4$, the CPU of the Cluster outperforms that of the laptop. The reduced chi-squared values of both fits are satisfactory in both cases, with a mild overfitting for the Noether Cluster model. Plot by Luis Miguel Villar Padruno.

B More on Thermal Effects

This work noted that accounting for thermal effects is essential to interpret the results correctly. Although assessing thermal throttling was beyond the scope of this study, several plots reveal these effects.

When the Drell–Yan simulations were redone on the laptop, it was observed that the CPU’s power consumption was correlated with the hardware temperature. It was found that the results were highly dependent on room temperature and the cooling system; for instance, when an external fan was used, the CPU power consumption stabilised at around 80 W, far exceeding the ~ 55 W that had been measured.

On the other hand, deviations from the proposed model, which assumes a constant efficiency at large n , are shown by plots of the number of events over the energy drawn on the Noether Cluster. In Figure A.8, for $n > 10^6$, a peak followed by a decline in energy efficiency is exhibited by the data. As noted in the main text, an insufficient number of data points were collected on the laptop to capture this effect, and therefore, the comparison cannot be considered entirely fair.

C Geographical Dependence

The Carbon Intensity, CI is heavily location-dependent, meaning that where software is run has a significant impact on the resulting CO_2e emissions, as illustrated in Figure C.10.

Fig. C.10. Map showing the CO_2e emission rate associated with running HERWIG across different countries. The average consumption used for the calculation of the rates was taken to be 362.76 W, as measured by Prometheus. Map by Luis Miguel Villar Padrino.

Bearing this fact in mind is essential for an international collaboration like the WLCG, which relies on computing resources distributed across multiple countries.